

The Unknown Simon Kuznets: Correspondence with his relatives in 2009– 2010

Vladimir M. Moskovkin

Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Independent Researcher, Vimperk, Czech
Republic

ORCID: 0000-0001-5587-4133

E-mail: researchhoa52@gmail.com

Abstract: This paper presents an expanded and annotated collection of correspondence between the author and the direct descendants of the Nobel Prize winner Simon Kuznets, including his son Paul Kuznets, his daughter Judith Stein, and his niece Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman. Covering the period from April 3, 2009 to March 3, 2010, the correspondence sheds light on previously unknown aspects of the Kuznets family's early biography, their life in the Russian Empire and Soviet Ukraine (Pinsk, Rovno, Kharkov), and their eventual emigration to the United States. By integrating original English letters with detailed Russian commentary (now translated for an international audience), this work corrects several historical inaccuracies regarding Kuznets' birthplace, his education at the Kharkov Commercial Institute, and the fate of his family members. This archival reconstruction serves as a critical resource for historians of economic thought and biographers of Simon Kuznets.

Keywords: Simon Kuznets, Solomon Kuznets, Georg Kuznets, Nobel Prize in Economics, history of economic thought, archival research, Kharkov Commercial Institute, Paul Kuznets, Judith Stein, Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman, scientific biography, emigration.

Preface

Initially, an overview of my correspondence with Simon Kuznets' relatives—his son Paul Kuznets, his daughter Judith Stein, and the daughter of Simon Kuznets' younger brother George, Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman—was published in Russian in April 2010 in the Kharkiv Jewish newspaper [1].

This correspondence took place from April 3, 2009, to July 24, 2009. Subsequently, comments on the letters were added to the overview, starting from the autumn of 2009 and ending on March 3, 2010.

As a result, an overview of this correspondence from April 3, 2009, to March 3, 2010, was published in the materials of the Nobel Congress – the 9th international meeting-conference of Nobelists (Tambov, Russia, September 27–29, 2010) [2].

It was reprinted in the materials of the XVI International Research Conference (Tambov, Russia, November 24–25, 2016) as an appendix to my article on the early biography of Simon Kuznets [3].

This article briefly describes the results of my correspondence regarding Simon Kuznets' research in Kharkov with Nobel Prize winner Robert Fogel, a student of Kuznets; his assistant Nathaniel Grotte; a researcher of the scientific economic heritage of the Jewish diaspora in the United States, Harvard economist Glen Weyl; the Columbia University archives, as well as unknown information about the early life of Simon Kuznets in the Russian Empire and Soviet Ukraine, which was revealed as a result of correspondence with Simon Kuznets' relatives. This work is interesting in that it was the first to publish copies of documents about Simon Kuznets' education in Kharkov, sent to me in August 2009 by Kuznets' daughter, Judith Stein. At the same time, the Russian translation of these documents was first published in article [4].

In the link to the PDF file of this 2016 article [3], the overview of correspondence with Simon Kuznets' relatives, published on pages 54-66, is missing. Below is an expanded version in English based on the 2010 edition. It includes expanded notes with references to sources and electronic copies of the most important letters. All new comments, additions to notes, and electronic copies of letters are highlighted in italics.

The Unknown Simon Kuznets: Correspondence with his relatives

V.M. Moskovkin

(Karazin Kharkov National University, Kharkov, Ukraine)

Knowledge of the past is not only found in newspapers, magazines, memoirs, archives, museums and libraries, but also in the living memory of people who witnessed past events, or who have preserved the memories of their friends and loved ones about them. However, after a few generations, these memories fade and, if not backed up by written evidence, disappear altogether.

All this perfectly describes the early life of a native of the Russian Empire, a resident of Belarus (Pinsk, 1901-1909) and Western Ukraine (Rovno, 1909-1915), a Jewish refugee in Eastern Ukraine (Kharkiv, 1915-1922), refugee-immigrant (1922-1928) and US citizen (1928-1985), winner of the 1971 Nobel Prize in Economics and outstanding economist of the 20th century, Simon Kuznets.

There are virtually no written records or published memoirs of his contemporaries about his life in the Russian Empire and Soviet Ukraine. In the existing encyclopaedic and biographical reference literature, there are two versions of S. Kuznets' place of birth. According to one, he was born in Kharkov, according to the other — in Pinsk. The first version was supported by S. Kuznets himself, since according to all official documents he was listed as a native of Kharkov.

After S. Kuznets' death in 1985, his widow, Edith Handler-Kuznets, clearly stated that he was born in Pinsk, not Kharkov, as noted in a footnote to S. Kuznets' obituary published in 1986 by his family friend Mozes Abramovitz [1]. No documentary evidence of this fact has been presented to date.

In this regard, on 3 April 2009, I turned to S. Kuznets' son, Paul Kuznets, a professor of economics at Indiana University (Bloomington). In his reply dated 11 April 2009, he reported:

“There is some confusion about his early life, but you are correct about his birthplace ... it was not Kharkov, but Pinsk...virtually nothing has been written about his personal life, sources of his thinking, or the impact of his early experience on the course of his scholarly work. I am not surprised by this, since he was close-mouthed about his early years. I learned this as a child when I asked him about his own earlier life and found that he did not want to talk about it. I suspect that the hardships imposed by World War I and the Revolution were responsible for his reticence.”

He noted that all he knew about his father's life in Kharkov was that he had been the head of the Southern Bureau of the Central Soviet Trade Union's statistical office in Ukraine before emigrating to the United States. He also told me about a letter from Nikolai Kostyukovich of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, who informed him about the installation in 2007 of a memorial plaque on the building in Pinsk where S. Kuznets is believed to have studied.

In a second letter dated 25 May 2009, he reported that after his father's death, his mother had transferred his documents and materials to the Harvard University archives [2] and that he doubted that there were any Russian-language documents among these papers, with the exception of S. Kuznets's well-known first scientific work [3]. At the same time, he noted, referring to the well-known work by Kapuria-Foreman and Perlman [4], that his father's second scientific work, written in Kharkov and devoted to Schumpeter's theory of innovation, had been translated into English and submitted as a master's thesis at Columbia University, where he studied. He doubts that it has been preserved in the archives of Columbia University [5].

From my extensive list of scholars and specialists who could have influenced S. Kuznets during his studies and work in Kharkov, he singled out only Tugan-Baranovsky, Slutsky, and Kondratyev, and even then only in the context of his own professional training as an economist. He also reported:

“I have no idea where, if anywhere, one could find a copy of my father's birth certificate, and I do not know when the Kuznets family moved from Pinsk to Kharkov”.

He recommended that I contact his sister, Judith Stein, who now lives in France, regarding these and other issues, which I did on 28 May 2009. Below is the text of that letter:

Dear Mrs. Judith Stein,

I'm interested in the early period of studies and work of Simon Kuznets in Kharkov. I corresponded with your brother Paul Kuznets and received detailed answers on my questions. But unfortunately, he couldn't help me with the problem I'm interested in. And he recommended to ask you all those questions in case you know the answers.

In order to brief you I attached my first letter to your brother.

Also, I would like to ask you some questions.

- 1. As Glen Weyl informed me your mother had gifted the archives of S. Kuznets to Harvard University library. So, is it possible that there can be Russian-language proofs of his work and studies in Kharkov?*
- 2. N. Kostyukovich (whose e-mail you gave me kindly) told me that the proofs of your father's birth in Pinsk haven't been found yet. How do you think are the copies of his certificate of birth kept in some American archives and where exactly?*
- 3. American researchers say that S. Kuznets has written the scientific paper dedicated to the analysis of Schumpeter's conception in Kharkov, which he presented as his master's assay to Mitchell. Is this information correct? And can this work be kept in the University of Columbia, where S. Kuznets defended his master's dissertation in 1924. Is there any possibility to order a copy of this work?*
- 4. You have written that your father didn't share his recollections of life in Kharkov with you (it was severe time with constant change of authorities, violence, terror, massacre, etc.) As far as I understand he also didn't speak about it with his colleagues and friends (judging by the letter I received from Robert Fogel). Is it so?*
- 5. Are you aware of the date when S. Kuznets' family moved from Pinsk to Kharkov? Kostukovich assumes that at that time S. Kuznets was really young. But if it is so he couldn't have graduated from municipal non-classical secondary school in Pinsk. But they have already built a memorial plaque after him.*
- 6. Could you ask your sister about all these things? And then tell me what she answered? Of course, if it is suitable.*

Gratefully,

Professor of Geography of the Kharkov National University (Ukraine),

Professor of World Economy of the Belgorod State University (Russia)

Vladimir M. Moskovkin.

P.S. There are some names of scientists and specialists from your father's circle, those people he used to deal with during his work and studies in Kharkov.

Has he ever mentioned any of them? And if he has then in what context?

- 1. Professors of the Kharkov University:*
 - V. F. Levitskiy*
 - M. N. Sobolev*
 - A. N. Antsyferov*
 - P. I. Fomin*
 - D. N. Ivantsov*

- *S. S. Zhilkin*
 - *M. E. Podtyagin*
2. *Specialists and consultants of Southern Bureau of Central Soviet Trade Union:*
- *I. Niselevich*
 - *V. Soloveyichik*
 - *F. Leibman*
 - *I. Schneider*
 - *I. Dubinskaya*
 - *A. Shulpin*
 - *E. Fritzel*
 - *I. Gavrilov*
 - *M. Kamentskiy*
 - *V. Gurevich*
 - *M. Buyanover*
 - *I.A. Trachtenberg*
3. *Russian researchers who didn't live in Kharkov those years but could have influenced him:*
- *Tugan-Baranovski*
 - *Kandratyev*
 - *Slutskiy*
 - *Petrushin*

May 28, 2009

I received the following reply to this letter (in this and subsequent letters, I have made notes in square brackets):

Dear Mr. Moskovkin,

*Please forgive me for not answering your letter sooner but I started looking for any material I might have that would be of interest to you and it took a while. As my brother said, our father did not talk about his childhood and youth very much but he did tell a few stories. More to the point, the daughter of my father's younger brother, George, wrote a short memoir of what her father recounted to her about his youth from which I can deduce that the family left Rovno where they lived with grandparents after leaving Pinsk - they arrived in Kharkov in 1915, thus my father would have been 14 years old. I have among my papers two translations of transcripts that were probably used by my father to enter Columbia University. One is a Department of Education certificate stating that my father entered Kharkoff High School #2 (*Kharkovskoye vtoroe Realnoye Ouchilische* [6]) in October 1916 and graduated in May 1917. The other is a report book from The Commercial Institute of Kharkoff [7] where he was accepted in 1918 and there are courses shown with marks for July 1921. He was also, and it must have been around the same time, the head of a section of the Bureau of Labor Statistics of the Ukraine during which time he wrote his first paper. As for your other questions -*

- 1) *I do not have any idea if there are any Russian language materials in the Harvard archive - surely if you write to them they can give you a list of what is contained there.*
- 2) *All of my father's immigration, visa and naturalization papers show him as having been born in Kharkov so I doubt very much that there is any proof of Pinsk to be found in the US. I believe that he was born in Pinsk but in order to leave Russia, or Poland, I think there was some falsifying of papers.*
- 3) *I don't know about his master's thesis, but it is certainly possible that there is a copy at Columbia University. I'm sorry that I don't recognize any of the names that you mention.*

I am trying to get an address or an e-mail address for my cousin - she may well be able to answer something for you or to give you some clues - when I get in touch with her, I will let you know.

If copies of the transcripts that I have (copies themselves) would be of interest, I would be glad to send them to you.

Sincerely, Judith K. Stein.

June 5, 2009

On 7 June, I wrote Judith Stein a second letter:

Dear Judith Stein,

I would like to thank you very much for your letter. It is the first one that throws the new light on our knowledge of your father's life in Kharkov.

Firstly, all of the encyclopaedic and biographic editions write that S. Kuznets studied in Kharkov University, and some of them specify that he studied there for two years. The Commercial Institute of Kharkov was established in 1917 on the basis of Kharkov Commercial School (founded in 1912) and was closed in 1921 and on its basis the Higher Party School was opened. Then it was reorganized into Communist Institute after Artem. The building of the former Commercial Institute of Kharkov (which was built 1914-1916 by famous architect of Kharkov A.N. Beketov) still remains and now Agrarian Technical University of Kharkov is situated there.

Second, we didn't know exactly about that he graduated Kharkoff High School #2 (Second real municipal school). Graduated students at such schools were able to enter to Higher Technical and Commercial Schools (Institutes), but not to the classical universities.

I would like to ask you few more questions:

1) *What year the family left Pinsk? And I wonder if you know where and how many years S. Kuznets studied in Pinsk (Belorussian journalists said that he studied in Pinsk at Real Municipal School);*

2) *And what year father of S. Kuznets moved to the USA? (In some sources it is said that it happened in 1914);*

3) *Why the family moved from Pinsk to Rovno and then to Kharkov? (The First World War, to provide the higher education to the children);*

4) *What year his brother George was born? (In the literature it is possible to find the information only about the elder brother Solomon);*

5) *What schools Solomon and George were studying at in Kharkov?;*

6) *Was he staying in touch with Russian immigrants and compatriots from USSR after he moved to the United States?;*

7) *Did S. Kuznets leave any memoirs (unpublished) from that time?*

8) *How do you think why the falsifying of his papers was needed? (The birth certificate was lost or for some reason it was not eligible for crossing the border or for naturalization, maybe it was done for getting a political asylum);*

9) *Do you know why there is a version that your father studied in Kharkov University? (Is it possible that S. Kuznets was using the word "university" as a synonym to a word "institute"?)*

I would really appreciate if you could send me those transcripts you have mentioned in your letter. Do you know where the Russian language originals of those transcripts can be? (In Columbia University, for example).

Sincerely

Prof. Vladimir M. Moskovkin

June 7, 2009

On 12 June, I received the following reply to this letter:

Dear Mr. Moskovkin,

I can answer a few of your questions, and perhaps guess at a few.

1) *I don't know when the family left Pinsk. According to my cousin, they left (this may be the answer to your question 3) to live with grandparents in Rovno [8]. I know nothing about my father's education in Pinsk.*

2) *My father moved to the US in 1922.*

3) *The family was expelled from Rovno (again according my cousin, all Jews were expelled for fear that they would collaborate with incoming Austrian and German*

armies [9]) This was in 1915.

4) George was born in 1909 in Kiev.

5) Maybe my cousin can answer this one.

6) As far as I know, no.

7) No - no memoirs at all.

8) I have the impression that for some reason it was not eligible for crossing the border - my knowledge of the complicated history of border changes in that region is minimal - is it possible that in order to get out, he would have needed to have been born in Kharkov rather than in Pinsk? When he left, he went to join his father in the US so there was no question of political asylum.

9) I don't know the answer to this one. In the talk that my father gave at his 80th birthday celebration he stated that he had "formal training in a scientific gymnasium" and also that he spent two years in an "institution devoted to economics." This talk is quoted by Robert Fogel in his afterword to the book of essays published after my father's death. The book is called "Economic development, the family, and income distribution, selected essays" - published by Cambridge University Press in 1989.

I will be happy to send you copies of the transcripts that I have – is there a way that I can send them by mail (non-electronic). I do not have a scanner. Please let me know an address.

I will be away for the next few weeks but will do it when I return. My cousin, Ruth Kuznets Pearson Hauptman, can be reached at birdsinger@gmail.com - she has said that she will be glad to see what she can answer for you.

Please let me know if I can help with any other questions.

Sincerely, Judith K.Stein

P.S. I see from reading the attachments to your original letter to me that Glen Weyl suggested some names for you to pursue (suggested to him by my brother, perhaps) - among those are both Owen Lattimore and Don Patinkin - these people have been dead for many years.

June 12, 2009

I lost Judith Stein's reply of 3 August 2009 to my third letter of 7 July 2009, but a summary of it was published in my 2010 correspondence.

Below, despite the duplication of information from Judith Stein's letters, I will review them in the same form as they were published in my 2010 correspondence.

In her first letter dated 5 June 2009, Judith Stein confirmed her brother's words that their father had told them practically nothing about his childhood and youth. She reported that her cousin, Ruth Kuznets-Hauptmann, the daughter of Simon Kuznets' younger brother Georg, had made brief notes of her father's memories, from which it follows that the family moved from Pinsk to Rovno, where she lived with grandfather and grandmother of S. Kuznets, and in 1915 the whole family moved to Kharkov. She reported that among her papers she found two translations of her father's educational documents, which were probably used by him when applying to Columbia University, issued by Kharkoff High School #2 (Kharkovskoye vtoroe Realnoye Ouchilische [6]) in May 1917 and The Commercial Institute of Kharkoff [7], to which he was admitted at the end of 1918, with the last grade dated July 1921 (a copy of the transcript of the record book). I should note right away that in late 1919 – early 1920, the Kharkov Institute of National Economy was established on the site of this institute and the law faculty of Kharkov University.

In 1921, S. Kuznets was already working as the head of the labour statistics sector of the statistics department of the Southern Bureau of the All-Union Central Council of Trade Unions, and, apparently, on 7 July 1921, he passed two subjects in statistics (theory and practice) as an external student at the latter institute (*Kharkov Institute of National Economy*). At the same time, he published his first scientific work [3].

In her first letter to me, Judith Stein also wrote that all immigration and visa documents, as well as her father's naturalisation documents, show that he was born in Kharkov, so she very much doubts that any evidence of his birth in Pinsk can be found in the United States. She expressed confidence that her father was born in Pinsk, but that documents had been falsified in order to leave Russia or Poland.

In a second letter dated 12 June 2009, Judith Stein, referring to her cousin, informed me that the family had left Pinsk to reunite with their parents in Rovno [8], and that her departure for Kharkov took place in 1915 in connection with the expulsion of Jews from the frontline zone due to the Russian tsarist government's fear that they would collaborate with Austrian and German troops [9].

When I asked her why her father's documents had been falsified, she replied that her knowledge of the complex history of border changes was minimal, but that perhaps Kharkov was a much more desirable place of birth than Pinsk for the purpose of emigrating from Russia to the United States.

She goes on to write that Kuznets' desire to leave Russia was linked to his wish to reunite with his father in the United States, so he cannot be considered a political refugee.

When I asked her another question about the persistent but erroneous claim that Kuznets studied at Kharkov University, she replied that she did not know the answer. However, she did reveal an important detail: at his 80th birthday celebration, he stated that he had “formal training in a scientific gymnasium” and also that he spent two years in an “institution devoted to economics”.

She noted in her letter that these words of her father were quoted by Robert Fogel in his afterword to the book *Economic Development, the Family, and Income Distribution, Selected Essays*, published in 1989 by Cambridge University Press. In the same letter, Judith Stein gave me her cousin's email address (Ruth Kuznets Pearson Hauptman) and asked me to send her my postal address so that she could send me copies of the documents.

In her third letter, dated 3 August 2009, which I received by post together with copies of her father's documents, she answered a number of my questions concerning her relatives. She confirmed the information known from literature that S. Kuznets' parents were involved in the fur business, and that his father continued this business in the United States. She stated that she did not know their dates of birth and death. She clarified that her father arrived in the United States in March 1922 together with his older brother Solomon. Solomon was a year or two older than Simon Kuznets. She also provided an unknown detail that S. Kuznets' younger brother Georg was born in Kiev in 1909, noting that the three brothers were economists. She recommended checking all the details of the Kuznets family's life with her cousin.

On 24 June 2009, I sent Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman a long letter asking her to clarify some unknown events from the early period of S. Kuznets' life. On 28 June

2009, she replied that she did not have a copy of her memoirs, which had been mentioned by her cousin Y. Stein, and asked for time to write down everything she knew about the early life of her father Georg and her uncle Simon.

On 24 July 2009, I received her long-awaited reply, which shed light on unique and previously unknown details of the Kuznets family's life. *Given the importance of this letter, I am reproducing it in full with my references to notes in square brackets:*

Dear Professor Moskovkin,

All my information is filtered through the eyes of my father, George Kuznets, as a child (and then mine again), so this must be taken into consideration as to its accuracy. Also, since it is mostly from a child's perspective, what I have written is quite informal. My cousin Judith Stein encouraged me to go ahead tell all from my point of view.

The "memoir" to which my cousin refers was in fact just a handwritten collection of memories my mother asked me to write after my father's death in 1986. The intent of that paper was for my mother's own use. It was also used to help prepare my father's official memorial biography written by his colleague, Professor Ivan Lee, at University of California. Quite a bit more of this information than I had anticipated was presented in my father's official biography. (University of California: In Memoriam, 1986) [10]. Apparently, my mother passed around copies of my handwritten paper. I don't remember discussing this with her, but that was a long time ago. I was surprised to find recently that my cousin Judith Stein has a copy of this paper [11]. I do not have a copy myself.

1) What year the family left Pinsk? And I wonder if you know where and how many years S. Kuznets studied in Pinsk (Belorussian journalists said that he studied in Pinsk at Real Municipal School);

I believe they left Pinsk in 1909 shortly after my father's birth, at about the same time Abraham Smith [12] left for the United States. My father told me Abraham left for the U. S. when he, my father, was two months old. I have now found that Abraham Smith may have left before that time, come back to Pinsk for a while, and then left again in 1909. At any rate, Uncle Simon would have been eight years old at the time, so could not have studied for too many years in Pinsk. If it was not 1909 when the family went to Rovno, it was before my father's conscious memory, within the next few years.

2) *Why the family moved from Pinsk to Rovno and then to Kharkov? (The First World War, to provide the higher education to the children);*

Pinsk to Rovno: I was given the impression by both my father and Aunt Edith that the family moved to Rovno for the education of the boys. I believe Rovno was a center of education for Jewish young people at the time [13].

The household in Rovno consisted of: The three boys, their mother Polina/Pescha, their unmarried aunt Eva/Yeva, their maternal grandparents the Friedmans, Schmucl and China (my father's spelling, I think Khina might be a better transliteration) [14]. Whether the Friedman's already lived in Rovno or came with the family from Pinsk, I don't know. I think at one time I was under the impression they were from Rovno, but I don't remember why or if that is accurate.

An aside here: the Kuznets family came from Stolin, and Abraham's father was named Alko-Wolfe Kuznets and remained in Stolin. I do not know the origins of the Friedman family.

Rovno to Kharkov: According to my father, in 1915 during the First World War one could see the front moving toward Rovno. Fire was visible in the distance and loud explosions were heard. My father said that "the Czar's Uncle," who was a Russian general, ordered the expulsion of Jewish people from this area because he was afraid of collaboration with German-speaking people. They were given 24 hours to prepare to leave and could only take what could be carried with them. My father remembers his grandfather burying valuables (silver candle sticks, etc.) under a cherry tree in the yard.

They left on a train which traveled through the Ukraine picking up and dropping off refugees along the way. I do not know why the family ended up in Kharkov.

3) *What year your father George was born? (In the literature it is possible to find the information only about the elder brother Solomon);*

My father was born in 1909 in Kiev. I have seen the birth record. His mother was in poor health and his birth was planned to take place at a medical center in Kiev.

4) *What schools Solomon and George were studying at in Kharkov?*

I can't answer this. My father told a story about his two older brothers preparing him for an entrance exam into a good school and my father failing, which was a big disappointment to all. He was still quite young, and he said, because of the difficult times, "his education had been neglected" [15]. Solomon and Simon both

studied in Kharkov, but I do not know where.

5) Was S. Kuznets staying in touch with Russian immigrants and compatriots from USSR after he moved to the United States?

Other than his own family, I do not know.

6) Did S. Kuznets leave any memoirs (unpublished) from that time?

I have no knowledge of this, and I doubt it.

7) How do you think why the falsifying of his papers was needed? (the birth certificate was lost or for some reason it was not eligible for crossing the border or for naturalization, maybe it was done for getting a political asylum)

I am not sure, but here is what my father told me: After the civil war in the Ukraine, the refugees from the western area (mostly Jewish) were sent back to the west on a train that snaked through the Ukraine picking up people along the way. This was 1921 as I remember my father telling it, but it is possible it was 1922. The borders had changed, and Rovno, Pinsk and I believe Stolin were all on the Polish side of the border now [16].

After the train crossed into Poland, in Rovno, Simon was arrested [17]. He was accused of spying or some such thing and there was talk of execution. After several days, the authorities found the “real spy”; it had been a case of mistaken identity, and Simon was released. This all sounds a little surreal to me. At this point in time I’m sure it would be impossible to find out what really happened. After this Simon and Solomon went to what was then Danzig, not under Polish control [18], and it was from there that they emigrated. I do not know about U.S. immigration quotas from Eastern Europe in 1921/1922, but there may have been a quota issue. There have also been hints of “escape” from Poland for Simon and Solomon.

They had both worked for what my father called the “Western Bolshevik Command Unit.” Or maybe this “Command Unit” somehow oversaw the bureau they worked for. I don’t know if this is the same thing as the Bureau Allrussian Central Council of Trade Union. With this history, things in Poland may have been difficult for them.

(While in Kharkov, Uncle Simon had papers from this Bolshevik authority allowing travel on the Dnieper River. When he traveled, he tried to pave the way for the family’s return to the Rovno/Pinsk area but apparently was unable to do so, and

returned to Kharkov without contacting relatives/friends on the other side of the border. Making such contacts was apparently dangerous in those times.)

In any case, for some reason emigration from Poland was not possible for Simon and Solomon, so they had to leave from Danzig where they apparently used falsified papers.

I remember my father and Uncle Simon having a discussion about Simon's immigration. Simon called himself an "escapee" or "refugee" or something like that, and my father disagreed and said that Simon had been an immigrant. Unfortunately, I do not remember or did not hear any further substantiating details on either side. (Uncle Simon may have been referring to escaping the later devastation of World War Two.)

While Simon and Solomon went to Danzig to prepare for emigration, my father and the four other adults in the family went to Warsaw where they took up residence in an apartment at Djika 21 [19]. It is possible Simon and Solomon also went to Warsaw for a short while before they left for Danzig. It is also possible the family went to Pinsk for a short while before they went to Warsaw, but if they did, I have not heard about this.

When their mother Polina was clearly not going to live much longer, in 1925 or 1926, Simon and Solomon came back to visit her, and they all met in Danzig since the young men were not able to enter Poland, or it was unwise to do so.

8) Do you know why there is a version that S. Kuznets studied in Kharkov University? (Is it possible that S. Kuznets was using the word "university" as a synonym to a word "institute"?)

I do not know.

I would like to ask you some extra questions.

1. What year did S. Kuznets' father move to the United States? (We have an information that he moved there in 1914)

See question #1 above. If it were 1914, I don't know why my father would have said this happened shortly after his birth in 1909.

2. Did he move to the USA from Pinsk or from Rovno?

I believe from Pinsk.

3. Also, we have an information that S. Kuznets moved to the USA from Pinsk-Warsaw 1922.

How do you think if it is possible or not? (Judith Stein told us that S. Kuznets arrived to the United States with a Kharkov birth certificate and in this case there wouldn't have been a need to move from Pinsk-Warsaw).

See question #7 above.

4. Did your father George Kuznets mention any people while he was living in Kharkov in his stories?

No, other than family, German and Austrian soldiers, Trotsky and Zinoviev whom he heard speak, Russian-speaking children with whom he associated where he lived, and characters with no names (e. g. "an old man").

I heard my father and Uncle Simon mentioning names. I don't know if the people to whom they referred were from Kharkov. I did not know nor do I remember any of these names.

5. At what address did the Kuznets family lived in Kharkov?

I don't know, but I can give a detailed description of the place - according to my father. It was a refugee home since housing was difficult to find - a deserted storefront (my father's term) on a main street on the edge of Kharkov at the time. It was originally owned by a man who lived in an estate next to the area. At one time I knew this man's name, now I have forgotten. It may be in the "memoir" that my cousin Judy speaks of. Behind the storefront was an amusement park, across the street a theater. The Austrians took over this area for a while; the estate owner eventually left. The street where they lived was one on which German soldiers marched into Kharkov to take over the city during WWI[20]. The estate next to the storefront was taken over as sort of a command post or headquarters by the Germans. The theater across the street was used as a holding place for prisoners of war. My father witnessed people being shot in front of this theater. There was a shed on the estate where an airplane was kept and guarded by a soldier. The amusement park turned into a high crime, dangerous area over time. Then came the civil war and I'm not sure what happened in this area of Kharkov, but I think eventually it became safer. However, I believe during the civil war there was a famine of sorts.

Apparently, the family did their best to make a real home under these conditions, and continued the education of their sons. They traveled from Kharkov to Odessa

at least once for some kind of cure for their mother's health, which was a holiday for my father.

Polina died in 1926. My father came to the U. S. shortly before his 18th birthday in 1927[21]. His aunt (and her new husband) and grandparents stayed in Warsaw. His father Abraham [22] had recently become a citizen and my father was able to enter with derivative citizenship since he was not yet 18. Immigration from Eastern Europe to the U. S. was pretty much closed by then.

I am attaching a photograph of the three Kuznets boys, from left to right George, Simon, Solomon, taken in Rovno I believe. My guess is it was in 1912 or 1913. The two older boys, Simon and Solomon appear to be wearing school uniforms. Maybe you can tell from their clothing where they were and what kind of school they were attending [23].

Please feel free to ask any other questions, but as you can see, my information is of an informal family nature and I know little about Uncle Simon's education or career.

Sincerely, Ruth Kuznets Hauptman

July 24, 2009

Comparing the information in this letter with the copies of two visa documents sent by Y. Stein, we can assume that S. Kuznets' trip to Danzig in 1923 was connected with the need to see his mother due to her very poor health (Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman suggested that this was in 1925 or 1926). His second trip to Germany in 1927 was obviously connected with sending his younger brother Georg to the United States after their mother's death and their father's acquisition of American citizenship [21].

In autumn 2009, I sent letters to Y. Stein and Ruth-Kuznets Hauptman, in which I shared all the details I had discovered about Simon Kuznets's places of study and residence in Kharkov.

On 6 February 2010, I received a reply from the latter, who thanked me for identifying the Kuznets family's place of residence in Kharkov and informed me that the surname of the Greek entrepreneur G. Mussuri did not ring any bells with her. She also wrote that:

“At one time I knew the name of the gentleman who lived on the estate and supposedly owned the amusement park. My memory is something like Golub, I really have forgotten.”

When I asked her to provide more detailed information about Solomon Kuznets, she replied:

“I believe Uncle Solomon almost had a doctorate but instead of finishing it chose to work for a Jewish organization. He was interested in establishing a state of Israel. He had two children, Henry and Paula. Apparently, Henry is in poor health now, and Paula died in 1980. Both Uncle Solomon and his wife died in 1945, leaving two young children who were raised by their maternal grandmother. As an adult, Henry had his surname officially changed to his grandmother's surname, Horwitz”.

In her next letter dated 14 February 2010, Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman reported that Judith Stein had more information about Henry Horwitz. She expressed doubts that he had any archives or information about his father's life in Kharkov, as his father had died when he was still very young. She once again expressed her gratitude to me for more accurately determining the Kuznets family's place of residence in Kharkov and said that her father may have mentioned the name Mussuri.

The day before, on 13 February, I received a letter from Y. Stein, who informed me that she had nothing written by her father in Russian. She then provided some rather important information, which we will quote verbatim:

“I did come across a few notes written by my mother, probably after my father died but I am not certain - I can now determine a few dates, I think. My grandfather, Abraham, was born in Stolyn, the family lived in Pinsk where my father was born (April 30, 1901 of the Gregorian calendar and April 17 of the Julian.) His brother Solomon was a year older. The family, without the father, moved to Rovno around 1907 and to Kharkov in 1915. Abraham remained in Pinsk, where he worked in a bank, and moved to the US in 1910, a year after George was born. According to my mother's notes, Simon and Solomon went to different schools in Kharkov because of Jewish quotas. As you know, my father went to two schools in Kharkov, and then spent two

years working before going to Poland in 1921 - apparently the family moved to Poland after the Peace Treaty of 1921 which allowed natives of Pinsk to return to what became Poland - they in fact went to Warsaw -- Simon and Solomon went to the US to avoid military service. My father became a US citizen in 1928.”

In her letter dated 3 March 2010, Simon Kuznets' daughter confirmed her cousin's statement that Henry Horwitz knew nothing about his father Solomon Kuznets' life in Kharkov, as he was only six years old when his father died.

Taking into account the new information we received in correspondence with S. Kuznets' relatives, it is necessary to intensify archival research in Pinsk, begin such research in Rovno and Warsaw, and continue it in Kharkov. As for Kharkov, it should be noted that there are no archives of the Kharkov Second Real School, the Kharkov Commercial Institute, or the Kharkov Merchant Society in the Kharkov State Archives. The Kharkov Institute of National Economy fonds in this archive is very small, consisting of 36 personal files of students and a list of students for the 1920 academic year. There are no materials relating to S. Kuznets here. The Archival collections of the Southern Bureau of the All-Union Central Council of Trade Unions, where S. Kuznets worked, should be sought in Kiev, Saint Petersburg, or Moscow.

The author would like to thank Yuliana Yurievna Polyakova, chief bibliographer of the Scientific and Bibliographic Department of the Central Scientific Library (V.N. Karazin Kharkov National University), for her assistance in identifying the Kuznets family's place of residence in Kharkov.

Literature for the Preface

1. Vladimir Moskovkin. Neizvestnyy Semon Kuznets. Perepiska s rodstvennikami i arkhivno-istoricheskiye izyskaniya (Unknown Semyon Kuznets. Correspondence with relatives and archival and historical research). Digest E. – April, 2010. - No. 4 (129). (in Russian).

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https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Vladimir-Moskovkin/publication/341354080_Neizvestnyj_Semen_Kuznec_perepiska_s_ego_rodstvennikami/links/5ebd1fed299bf1c09abbe25c/Neizvestnyj-Semen-Kuznec-perepiska-s-ego-rodstvennikami.pdf

3. Moskovkin, V.M. Unknown Semen Kuznets: Takes Us into the Early Period of His Life. The Formation of Professional in the Conditions of the Region: New Approaches: (Materials of the XVI International Research Conference), Nov. 24-25, 2016, Tambov (Russia) / Senior Editor Prof. V.M. Tyutyunnik. – Tambov; Moscow; S.-Petersburg; Baku; Vienna; Hamburg; Stockholm: “Nobelistics” IINC Publ. House, 2016. – P.43-66. (in Russian).

https://www.elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_29235707_88086373.pdf

4. Moskovkin, V.M. (2010). Neizvestnyy Semen Kuznets: ucheba v Kharkove [Unknown Simon Kuznets: studying in Kharkov]. *Universitates: science and education*, 1, 52–65. (in Russian). <http://dspace.bsuedu.ru/handle/123456789/902>

Notes

1. Abramovitz, Mozes (1986). Simon Kuznets (1901-1985). *The Journal of Economic History*, 46(1), 241-246. This article was translated into Russian by E.I. Nikolaenko and published in the collection: Thesis. — Moscow, 1992. — Vol. 1, issue 2. — pp. 228–234.

2. Harvard University Archives: HUGFP 88.45 [Lecture notes, speeches, manuscripts and other papers, 1923-1981 (6 boxes)]. The existence in this fund of a draft version of S. Kuznets' master's thesis (Dr. Schumpeter's System Presented and

Criticized. Columbia University, 1924, 109 p.) with handwritten corrections and notes by his supervisor, Wesley Mitchell, was pointed out by Mark Perlman in his work "Two phases of Kuznets's interest in Schumpeter" (2001). Our request to this archive on 14 October 2009 did not reveal the existence of Russian-language documents dated 1923-1924 (box 1), according to the response received on 3 November 2009 from Robin Carlow (Researcher, Harvard University Archives, Pusey Library).

3. Kuznec, Sem. (1921). Denezhnaya zarabotnaya plata rabochih i sluzhashchih fabrichno-zavodskoj promyshlennosti g. Har'kova v 1920 godu. *Materialy po statistike truda na Ukraine (Har'kov)*, 2 (Iyul'), 53-64. [*Kuznets, Sem. (1921). Cash wages of workers and employees in the factory and plant industry of Kharkiv in 1920. Materials on labour statistics in Ukraine (Kharkov)*, 2 (July), 53-64]. (in Russian). This article has been reprinted by us in the appendix to the article: *Moskovkyn, V. (2002). Semen Kuznets: Eho professional'noe okruzheniye v Har'kove i pervaya nauchnaya rabota [Semen Kuznets: His Professional Environment in Kharkov and the First Scientific Work]. Business Inform (Kharkov)*, 9-10, 83-99.] (in Russian).
http://dspace.bsu.edu.ru/bitstream/123456789/432/1/Moskovkin_Kuznets_2.pdf

4. Kapuria-Foreman, V., Perlman, M. (1995). An Economic Historian Economist: Remembering Simon Kuznets. *The Economic Journal*, 105 (November), 1524-1547.

5. My correspondence with the Columbia University archives in October 2009 not only revealed the final version of S. Kuznets' master's thesis, but also established the existence of an interesting master's thesis by his older brother Solomon entitled "Cournot and Marshall: A Comparative Study," which he defended in 1925 at Columbia University. As a result of this correspondence, it became clear that the Columbia University archives did not contain any Russian-language documents by S. Kuznets about his studies in Kharkov. *S. Kuznets' thesis in Russian was published in a book with our introductory article: Moskovkin, V.M., Mykhailychenko D.Yu. (2013). Simon Kuznets and the Kharkiv Higher School of Economics at the*

beginning of the 20th century). In V.S. Ponomarenko (Ed.), *Kuznets S. Dr. Schumpeter's Economic System, Explained and Criticised* (pp.7-34). Kharkiv: Publishing House "INZHEK". (in Russian).

<https://repository.hneu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/21797>

6. In fact, there were two certificates of graduation from Kharkov Second Real School: 1. Enrolled on 26 October 1915 and graduated on 16 May 1917 (eight marks of 5, five marks of 4); 2. Enrolled on 1 September 1917 (post-graduate course) and graduated on 31 May 1918 (twelve marks of 5, two marks of 4 and one mark of 3 in physics). *See Preface.*

7. According to a translated copy of S. Kuznets's academic record book, he enrolled at the Kharkov Commercial Institute at the end of 1918 (Assistant Rector — M. Sobolev) and passed eight subjects in his first year, taught by such renowned Russian economists as Professor V. F. Levitsky and Professor P. I. Fomin. *At the end of 1919 and beginning of 1920, the Kharkov Institute of National Economy was established on the site of this institute and the law faculty of Kharkov University.*

8. On the maternal side of S. Kuznets, Polina Kuznets.

9. By order of the commander-in-chief, Grand Duke Nikolai Nikolayevich, and the chief of staff of the General Headquarters, General N. Yanushkevich, the entire Jewish population was expelled from most of the Courland (28 April 1915) and Kovno (15 May 1915) provinces (Electronic Jewish Encyclopedia, www.eleven.co.il). At the same time, Jews were also being expelled from the Volyn province, where Rovno was located at the time.

10. This biography was posted online in 2007 on the Calisphere biographical portal (<https://digicoll.lib.berkeley.edu/record/81149?v=pdf>). The first part is very similar to the text of Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman's letter to me.

11. Judith Stein mentioned this manuscript in a letter to me, but did not write that she had it.

12. Abraham Kuznets (Smith)— father of Simon, Solomon and Georg

13. This is confirmed by information from the Electronic Jewish Encyclopedia.

14. The Kuznets brothers' maternal grandparents.

15. In this regard, the official memorial biography of Georg Kuznets, published in University of California: In Memoriam, 1986, notes: "The stop at Kharkov turned out to be a chaotic six-year stay, during which time George's formal schooling was sporadic at best. He compensated for this by reading extensively, a practice which he continued throughout his life, P.161."

<https://digicoll.lib.berkeley.edu/record/81149?v=pdf>

16. Our monitoring of the press during the peace talks in Riga revealed the following details. On 12 October 1920, a preliminary peace treaty and armistice were signed with Poland. Their terms recognised the independence of Ukraine and Belarus. The border was established along the Dvina River from the Latvian border to the Desna River, then south through the Orekhovo station along the Polotsk-Molodechno railway 20 versts east of Molodechno and 30 versts east of Vileika, then beyond the Kolosovo station, then along the Lan River to Pripyat, then beyond the Rakitno station through Korets, Ostok and Shumsk along the Sbruch River to the Dniester. Thus, Polotsk and Minsk remained within Russia. The treaty had to be ratified through the Rakitno, through Korets, Ostok and Shumsk along the Sbruch River to the Dniester. Thus, Polotsk and Minsk remain within Russia. The treaty must be ratified within 15 days. The armistice begins on 18 October and will last for 21 days (Peace with Poland // Economic Life. — 1920. — 14 Oct.). Russia and Ukraine undertake to re-evacuate the property of local authorities, institutions, individuals and legal entities that was taken from Polish territory to Russia and Ukraine from 1 August 1914. All property without exception is subject to re-evacuation, such as: personal property, jewellery, cash, securities, dead and live inventory, production tools, archives, libraries, collections, etc. (Polish proposal of 25 November on the re-evacuation of private property // Economic Life. — 1920. — 30 November). On 24 February 1921, an agreement was signed on the repatriation of all hostages, civilian prisoners, internees, prisoners of war, refugees and emigrants within the RSFSR, the USSR and the Polish Republic, concluded in

accordance with Article VII of the preliminary peace terms. On the basis of the agreement, no later than ten days from the date of signing, i.e. 6 March of this year, the transport of prisoners of war should begin, which will take place even before the formation of mixed Russian-Ukrainian-Polish commissions on repatriation (On peace negotiations with Poland // Pravda. — 1921. — 1 March).

Thus, by March 1921, Simon Kuznets and his family had all the information related to the change of borders, the upcoming re-evacuation of property and the repatriation of people. These circumstances, as well as the high probability of military mobilisation of Simon and Solomon, forced the Kuznets family, in our opinion, to look for quick, illegal ways to send their adult children overseas.

17. During the First World War and later, until the military and political situation in Eastern Europe stabilised, Jews were often arrested as hostages or on charges of espionage.

18. After World War I, Danzig (Gdańsk) was granted the status of a free city under the Treaty of Versailles (1919) and was placed under the administration of the League of Nations. In 1939, it came under German control.

19. *The official memorial biography of Georg Kuznets about the Polish period of the Kuznets family's life states the following: “In 1921, the refugees were sent back to the towns in the western Ukraine from whence they came in 1915, but Rovno was now in Poland due to a boundary shift resulting from the Russo-Polish War. At that point the two older brothers emigrated to the United States, and the remaining family took up residence in the Warsaw ghetto, where George attended gymnasium. In late 1926, upon the death of his mother, Kuznets left Warsaw for Paris to await clearance of his visa for emigration to the United States.”* (<https://digicoll.lib.berkeley.edu/record/81149?v=pdf>).

20. From the history of Kharkov, it is known that the Germans entered the city on 26 March 1918 (at 10 a.m. they were on Kholodnaya Hora) and initially marched along Ekaterinoslavskaya Street. According to Y. Y. Polyakova's theatre review in the journal *Universitates: Science and Education* (2008, No. 4), there were a large number of miniature and variety theatres on this and neighbouring streets at that

time: the Smolyakov, Volchin, Sarmatov, and Peltzer theatres on Ekaterinoslavskaya Street, the Tivoli Theatre (32 Blagoveshchenskaya Street), the Aquarium Theatre (36 Chebotarskaya Street), the Versailles Variety Theatre (1 Kontorskaya Street) and the Buff Theatre (18 Blagoveshchenskaya Street). Some of these theatres fit her description: “In 1902, there were several gardens in Kharkov with “summer theatres”, entertainment and buffets.” This is exactly what Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman describes: “Behind the storefront was an amusement park, across the street a theatre.” Our analysis of the cases of the Kharkov Provincial Presence Fund concerning refugees from the First World War (Kharkov State Archives) shows that the first wave of refugees (1915) were housed in the Mussuri theatre - circus, located at 28 Blagoveshchenskaya Street. At my request, Yuliana Yurievna Polyakova compared this information with the description of the Kuznets family's stay in Kharkov and concluded that the Kuznets family lived in a refugee house (the Mussuri theatre-circus), and that the nearby Tivoli amusement park was the very same amusement park and theatre of the same name that Ruth Kuznets-Hauptman wrote about. The Mussuri theatre-circus building (later a Musical comedy theatre) has survived to this day and is currently mothballed. The Tivoli amusement park and the theatre building have not been preserved. The Yuzhnaya Hotel now stands on the site of this building.

21. The official memorial biography of Georg Kuznets states that he lived in Paris for nine months before leaving for the United States, waiting for his visa to be issued. In this regard, it is important to note that on Simon Kuznets' visa document (which I received from Y. Stein), issued by the German Consulate General in New York on 8 July 1927, the last stamp was affixed in Cherbourg (France) on 20 September 1927. Therefore, it is obvious that Simon Kuznets specifically travelled to Europe in 1927 to take his younger brother to his father in the United States. Upon his arrival in the United States, he studied English at Columbia University and, after some time, moved with his father to Southern California (Sierra Madre), and all of his further education and scientific career were connected with the University of California.

22. It is important to note the rational choice of place of residence by Abram Kuznets in the USA. Being involved in the fur business, he chose a mountainous and forested region of the USA (California), which was most suitable for his professional interests.

23. The analysis of Internet sources (official portals and websites of Rovno) shows with a high degree of probability that Simon Kuznets studied at the Rovno Real School, from which the famous writer V.G. Korolenko graduated with a silver medal in 1873. *This was later confirmed through archival research: Moskovkin, V., Samsonyuk, T. (2012). Obucheniye bratyev Semena i Solomona Kuznets v Rovenskom realnom uchilishche [Teaching Brothers Semen and Solomon Kuznets in the Rovno Real School]. Novyi Kolehium, 2, 75–83. (in Russian). <http://dspace.bsuedu.ru/bitstream/123456789/3236/1/Moskovkin%20Samsonyuk%20Obuchenie.pdf>*